

First Steps in Refining the Automation of Preliminary Orbital Determination using Asteroids 2023 RS and 2023 UJ7

Marina Stefanoni and Federica Spoto

December 12, 2023

Abstract

Determining preliminary orbits is integral in the process of designating new solar system objects (SSOs). This designation process can be improved through automation, and the level of automation efficiency relies on refining the basic parameters governing the submissions of observational data. The preliminary orbital determination methods cited in this paper require the submission of at least three distinct observations in order to have the capability of producing an initial orbit. We found that having greater time between observations helps reduce error in the computed initial orbit. However, the minimum time between the first and last observation allowing a preliminary orbit to be computed has yet to be researched. The Gauss [Gro04] and Laplace [Gro09] methods were used in addition to a higher order polynomial (degree 8) method to investigate how preliminary orbits changed with different time spans between observations. We ran a preliminary orbital determination process on different batches of observations of two asteroids designated 2023 RS and 2023 UJ7. The results of the test batches yielded the key result that both objects could have had preliminary orbits computed with fewer observations than were used in reality. This has valuable implications for planetary defense efforts especially concerning the near-earth asteroid 2023 RS.

1 Introduction

The Minor Planet Center (MPC) is the only location that receives and distributes observations of solar system objects (SSOs) from observatories across the world. Observations define the position of an object on the celestial sphere either geocentrically or through right ascension (RA) and declination (Dec) coordinates. Typically observations submitted to the MPC contain meta data such as the magnitude of the object or the type of telescope used. The MPC is responsible for the identification, designation, and orbital determination of all of these observed objects, so researchers tests to see whether these observations are of new SSOs or of previously designated objects. If the observations are of objects that are not known SSOs, a preliminary orbit must be computed before the object can be designated.

The process of observation acquisition to object designation is not entirely automated, making the process take more time than is optimal. The potential to increase efficiency is a key factor of the work that the MPC is looking into because of the millions of observations with which they must accept and work each year. Based on data submission statistics for 2023, the MPC receives between 2-3 million observations each month on average [Cen]. Of the millions of monthly observations submitted, the MPC is able to announce the discovery of more than 1000 minor planets each month and a couple hundred near-earth asteroid (NEA) discoveries. NEAs are of special interest to the MPC due to the potential that these objects could impact earth, making the timely orbital determination and designation of these objects vital. The ability to find a preliminary orbit quicker is valuable in understanding the risk associated with each object. Furthermore, the MPC is funded by and works closely with NASA, so the center plays an integral role in planetary defense efforts. Thus, a project has been started in an attempt to create a more efficient designation process.

The project includes code available through the Minor Planet Center that produces initial orbits for objects given there are at least three distinct observations as inputs. Then a differential corrections procedure can be run to obtain a final preliminary orbit. In order to learn how the code functions and understand the trends of preliminary orbits produced when the batches of observations were altered,

we looked at two designated asteroids: [2023 RS](#) and [2023 UJ7](#). We chose to use already designated objects in order to more reliably test the functions of the code and be able to reference the true orbital elements when looking at the code’s output.

The rest of this paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 discusses our methodology by first highlighting the two objects used for our analysis and then noting how the input of data was manipulated for the purpose of testing different batches of object observations. The final sub-sections discuss the code, orbital determination methods, and differential corrections leading to a final initial orbit. Results are presented in Section 3 with the aid of plots highlighting trends in orbital determination success and error for both asteroids. Section 4 summarizes our conclusions and offers a discussion of future work and potential improvements. Lastly, Section 5 acknowledges those who were integral in helping this paper come to fruition.

2 Methodology

2.1 Data

This sub-section looks at the objects used in our analysis and the format of data used throughout the orbital determination processes.

2.1.1 Objects of Interest

In conducting this research, we chose to look at two near earth asteroids designated 2023 RS and 2023 UJ7. Because the objects already have known orbits, we were able to compare the preliminary orbits from different batches with the known orbital elements. Table 1 and table 2 denote common orbital elements for 2023 RS and 2023 UJ7 respectively. Tables 3 and 4 summarize other characteristics of the objects and their observations. All values in the tables originate from the Minor Planet Center database [[Cen](#)].

SSO	Epoch	Distance (au)	Abs. Magnitude	a (au)	e	i (°)
2023 RS	2023-09-13.0	9.0e-05	32.32	1.76835	0.3953033	9.97754

Table 1: 2023 RS Orbital Elements (a,e,i) and Additional Characteristics (‘Epoch’ at which elements were computed, ‘Distance’ from earth at closest approach in astronomical units, and ‘Absolute Magnitude’)

SSO	Epoch	Distance (au)	Abs. Magnitude	a (au)	e	i (°)
2023 UJ7	2023-09-13.0	9.397e-02	23.24	2.3885191	0.5464161	5.50131

Table 2: 2023 UJ7 Orbital Elements (a,e,i) and Additional Characteristics (‘Epoch’ at which elements were computed, ‘Distance’ from earth at closest approach in astronomical units, and ‘Absolute Magnitude’)

2023 RS had a near encounter with earth being 9.0e-05 AU away at its closest distance on September 7th, 2023 at 2:26pm. Because the asteroid came so close to earth, it was observed many times in a short period of time. On the other hand, 2023 UJ7’s closest distance to earth was about 9.397e-02 AU. This further distance caused the object to be observed fewer times over a longer time span as it was not moving as quickly relative to 2023 RS. Furthermore, the absolute magnitude of both objects tells us about their relative sizes. Since the absolute magnitude of 2023 RS is 32.32 and 2023 UJ7 has an absolute magnitude of 23.24, we know that 2023 UJ7 is brighter. At these distances, the brightness of an object can also inform us about their relative sizes. 2023 RS is a smaller object than 2023 UJ7 and this makes it possible that observations may contain greater error due to the faster speed at which it is traveling past earth during its closest approach. Thus, the ability to compare the results of these two objects is useful because 2023 UJ7 represents more typical objects that are further away, being observed fewer times over a longer time span. On the other hand, 2023 RS was able to be observed a greater number of times over a much smaller time span due to its close and brief encounter.

SSO	Number of Observations	Time Span (days)	Observatory Codes
2023 RS	33	0.321576	G96, V37, V06, F65
2023 UJ7	12	5.841516	F52, H21

Table 3: Number of Observations, Time Span for 2023 RS and 2023 UJ7, and Observatory Codes (unique codes to indicate the observatory location from which an observation was made)

2.1.2 Format and Data Batching

The data used are in a standard 80-column format. Detailed information about which columns correspond to which values can be found on the [Minor Planet Center website](#). Table 3 organizes key information about the data available for each object in addition to the right ascension and declination at different observation times. The location of the asteroid on the celestial sphere is the information that the orbital determination methods use to compute the preliminary orbits. The observatory codes provided allow the MPC to know from where the objects were observed. From this, the relative locations of the observations can be quickly translated into the celestial coordinates. Asteroid 2023 RS was first observed at the start of the day on September 7, 2023 where the 33rd and final observation was made 7 hours and 43 minutes later. 2023 UJ7 was observed 12 times over a time span of 5 days, 20 hours, and 12 minutes beginning on October 17, 2023. For both objects, we split the observations into different batches in order to understand how preliminary orbits would change when the time span between each batches first and last observation was altered. Because 2023 RS has more observations, we started running batches through the preliminary orbital determination code for this object. This allowed us to get familiar with how the code functioned and how to read the output.

At least three observations are required for the orbital determination methods to function, so we first tested many batches of three observations for 2023 RS. Given that the code had to be re-run for each batch used and the data manually copied into a separate document, it was not feasible to run all combinations of observations for either object. After documenting the results for different batches of three observations, we took a more systematic route: starting from the first three observations, each batch would contain one more observation until the code was able to produce an orbit with adequate error (measurements of error employed for this project used will be discussed more thoroughly in Section 3). For example, batch 1 contains 2023 RS observations 1-3, batch 2 contains observations 1-4, and so on. This process was then repeated in reverse: beginning with the last three observations, the next most recent observation was added to the batch. This process allowed us to see at what time span a preliminary orbit could be computed and then at what time span a preliminary orbit with low error around the orbital elements could be computed.

The asteroid 2023 UJ7 was quicker to analyze due to there only being 12 observations with which to work. The same splitting and batching process was used in this case.

2.2 Preliminary Orbital Determination

Each batch of observations was run through the same code that is available through the Minor Planet Center. The code must be manually compiled before it is accessible and usable. In order to properly determine preliminary orbits, in addition to the force from other planets, the code accounts for the gravitational effects of the largest 17 minor planets in the solar system. Once the desired batch of observations is set to run through the program, the code prompts users with a menu of 16 available functions. There are only three functions necessary for computing an initial orbit: acquiring orbital elements, a differential corrections calculation, and a unit conversion function allowing orbital elements to be converted into Keplerian, Equinoctial, Cartesian, or Cometary (true anomaly). First, we select to acquire orbital elements for the batch of observations we have selected as inputs. From here, the code prompts us to select a method with which to compute a preliminary orbit. The methods used for this project are Gauss, degree 8 polynomial solutions, and Laplace. Each method requires at least three observations in order for them to be able to perform the orbital estimations. For more information on the mathematical processes of Gauss’s method, please refer to Giovanni F. Gronchi’s 2004 paper [Gro04]. The Laplace and higher degree polynomial equation methods are referenced in his other paper [Gro09].

The code is organized where the first option for computing the orbit uses the Gauss method, the

second uses the solutions to a degree 8 polynomial equation, and the final uses Laplace. This is not a preferential order, however the batches of observations were run through the methods in this order until an orbit could be computed. For example, if an orbit could not be computed using the Gauss method, we would re-run the same batch of observations through the polynomial solutions method. If this were to fail, then the last attempt at an initial orbit would be through Laplace. Only if all three methods have failed would the batch of observations be denoted as a failed orbit. The three methods individually succeed or fail at producing preliminary orbits depending on the amount of information and the geometry of the observations. Consequently, if only one method is able to properly compute an initial orbit, this does not mean that the output is untrustworthy.

Once a preliminary orbit is computed, the output shows up directly in the terminal through which we are running the code. The output at this stage is not the final orbit that we document. The next step is to run a differential corrections procedure in which a final preliminary orbit is found through an iterative least-squares minimization process [GDM10]. Often if we are working with a limited number of observations, the first computed orbit does not produce the most refined orbital elements. The differential corrections procedure is intended to improve the initial orbit when more observations cannot be gained [Gro04]. If any of the methods fail at this improvement step, the same process is followed where the batch of observations will be run through the subsequent method and the differential corrections procedure until an orbit is produced.

The orbital elements that we documented from the final preliminary orbital output was the semi-major axis (a) measured in astronomical units (AU), eccentricity (e), and perihelion distance (q) also measured in AU. Both the semi-major axis and eccentricity were measured in Keplerian coordinates, whereas the perihelion distance was documented in cometary coordinates. We compared the values of these elements for each successful preliminary orbit to the true orbital elements of the object to identify any trends in the data. Lastly, in order to find the error in the form of root mean square associated with produced elements, a separate document will automatically update each time the program is run and completed. Then from here we manually copy and pasted the results into one document containing all of the preliminary orbital elements. We were able to assess when different batches of observations for the two objects produced good preliminary orbits based on the ratio of the orbital element values to their root mean square (RMS) values. If this ratio is larger than 3, then we can be more certain about the orbit. There were many cases in which a test batch produced a preliminary orbit with elements close in value to the asteroid's true orbital elements. If the uncertainty was large enough, we still decided to reject the preliminary orbit.

3 Results

After running different batches of observations for the asteroids 2023 RS and 2023 UJ7, we saw some trends that we were expecting. First, adding more observations to subsequent batches creates a longer time between the first and last observation. By having more time between the bookend observations, the orbital determination methods have more information about the path of the object's orbit. We assumed that over time the computed orbital elements would trend toward the true values for each object. Figure 1 contains 3 plots of the time trends for 2023 UJ7's orbital elements (a , e , q). The dashed red lines on each plot indicate the true orbital element values for 2023 UJ7. The three plots illustrate that over time, the orbital elements trend toward their true values.

Figure 1: Three time plots of 2023 UJ7's orbital elements

In all three plots, there is a dramatic drop in the orbital elements toward their true values by the 3rd or 4th data point. Around 4.25 days of time (8-9th observation) since the asteroid was first viewed, we can see that the data points fall fairly close to the true value. Adding these observations seems to act as a threshold such that at this point it may have already been possible to compute a preliminary orbit for 2023 UJ7. This can be confirmed by looking at the uncertainties associated with the orbital elements.

Another trend that we assumed would occur is that as the number of observations increases, the RMS uncertainty should decline for the orbital elements. We can see this in Figure 2 and Figure 3 for both asteroids when looking at the RMS for the semi-major axis. The RMS was an important statistic to reference when deciding whether the preliminary orbit is good enough to allow for designation. If the code produced an orbit with large enough error, we elected to note it as a poor orbit. When 2023 UJ7's orbit was computed with 8 observations, the RMS for the semi-major axis was 0.2865. When 2023 RS's orbit was computed with 13 observations, the RMS for the semi-major axis was 0.2367. These values on their own are small, but do not tell us about the quality of the computed preliminary orbits. The next set of plots (Figure 4 and 5) help demonstrate when the quality of orbital elements is sufficient for a good orbit.

Figure 2: 2023 RS semi-major axis uncertainty

Figure 3: 2023 UJ7 semi-major axis uncertainty

In Figure 4 and 5 we plotted each object’s semi-major axis to RMS ratio as a function of the number of observations. With more observations, there was an increase in this value, indicating that the uncertainty for orbital elements declined with more observations. We chose to use 3-sigma (ratio of semi-major axis to semi-major axis uncertainty) rule in determining whether or not the orbital elements signify a good orbit. Thus, the dotted horizontal lines on the plot represent the 3-sigma value. Points on the two plots that lie above this threshold are considered usable for a preliminary orbit. Asteroid 2023 RS has uncertainty ratios larger than 3 for all the orbital elements starting after the 13th observation is added (2.5 hours between observations 1-13). 2023 UJ7 has uncertainty ratios larger than 3 after the 7th observation is added, corresponding to 4 days, 1 hour, and 14 minutes. Figures 4 and 5 highlight the observations at which the uncertainty ratio first exceeds a value of 3 (denoted by the dashed red line on each plot). We used all of the viable observations for 2023 UJ7, but elected to remove observations 26-33 for 2023 RS because they skewed the vertical scale. The semi-major axis to RMS ratio for the last few observations neared a value of 1000, so the change from a ratio smaller than 3 to one larger was impossible to view properly.

Figure 4: 2023 RS uncertainty ratio

Figure 5: 2023 UJ7 uncertainty ratio

These results indicate that both asteroids could have had preliminary orbits computed sooner and potentially designated more efficiently. This is less important for 2023 UJ7 given that it’s distance from earth does not pose a threat. However, because of 2023 RS’s proximity to earth when it was first detected, computing an orbit as quickly as possible will help planetary defense teams working with the data to be able to act earlier. With an automated system taking in observations as they come, the Minor Planet Center could have had information about the preliminary trajectory of this near-earth asteroid after 2.5 hours rather than waiting three times as long for the entire encounter of 7 hours and 43 minutes.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

These two objects describe two different SSO situations. 2023 UJ7 represents a more typical near-earth asteroid—one that we are not worried about impacting earth in the near future. On the other hand,

2023 RS is a small, quickly moving near-earth asteroid that had a very close encounter with earth. This object was detected only a few hours before its closest approach with earth, so this highlights the importance of being able to compute preliminary orbits as quickly as possible for NEAs. Working with millions of observations without an automated orbital determination system will allow potential threats to earth remain unnoticed for longer periods of time. The results presented in this paper are part of the first step in attempting to understand how the designation process can become more efficient through refined automation. Because no robust statistical analysis was conducted on the success of the preliminary orbits for different batches, we cannot generalize the results. By including this in future work on this project, researchers can begin to better understand the success rate of preliminary orbits given a certain time span between observations.

Furthermore, it could be of interest to researchers to test whether there is a significant difference in the accuracy of preliminary orbits from the different determination methods. Instead of running the new observations through the determination methods almost at random depending on the observational geometry, is there one method that tends to produce a low-error orbit more often? These are questions that could be answered by testing more objects and observation batches with the program.

5 Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my advisor Federica Spoto for her patience and guidance throughout this process. The Minor Planet Center must also be recognized for providing the data for the objects of interest, and to those who created the code to begin automating preliminary orbital determinations. Lastly, thank you to those who read this paper before its final version and to all of the AY98 class for their support throughout the semester.

References

- [Cen] Minor Planet Center. [Online; accessed November 25, 2023].
- [GDM10] G. F. Gronchi, L. Dimare, and A. Milani. Orbit determination with the two-body integrals. *Celestial Mechanics and Dynamical Astronomy*, 107(3):299–318, May 2010.
- [Gro04] Giovanni Federico Gronchi. Classical and modern orbit determination for asteroids. *Proceedings of The International Astronomical Union*, 2004, 06 2004.
- [Gro09] Giovanni Federico Gronchi. Multiple solutions in preliminary orbit determination from three observations. *Celestial Mechanics and Dynamical Astronomy*, 103, 04 2009.